

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SKILLS ON COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES THROUGH THE USE OF LOCAL NETWORKS

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Abstract. *The given article discusses the importance of network technologies in the educational process, regarding the use of local networks during lessons impacts on students' understanding of the subject matter and the role it plays in their learning. The process of forming students' informational knowledge and skills is analyzed.*

Keywords: *information and Communication Technologies, Informational Knowledge, Network Technologies, Distance Education, Innovative Education, Local Network Program.*

Introduction. At present time all higher educational institutions are equipped with modern computer and telecommunication equipment. This requires teachers to take a new approach to their work. The introduction of new technologies into the educational process does not lead to the displacement of the teacher by technical means, but to the improvement of pedagogical activity, a change in the tasks and role of the teacher [1].

For improving the efficiency of the educational process, modern information and communication technologies (ICT) are widely used. The role of network technologies in the development of information knowledge and skills of students is very important. Today, the learning process can be optimized and its efficiency increased using the Internet and various online platforms. The organization of the educational process using a local computer network is of great importance for the development of students' information processing skills.

In the era of modern information technology, significant changes are also observed in the field of education. Changes are also made to the content of computer science and information technology. Schoolchildren are taught the basics of modern programming and software. An urgent task is to develop students' information knowledge and skills using network technologies.

Methodology. Network technologies play an important role in expanding the possibilities of independent learning for students and developing their knowledge and skills. Network technologies include technologies such as the Internet, computer networks, cloud technologies, virtual and augmented reality. They create the following opportunities in education, and these factors are examples of this sphere.

What is more important, students will be able to quickly and conveniently find the information they need. Students can access the necessary knowledge and materials at any time via the Internet. Interactive teaching methods are used. Online classes, webinars, and virtual labs provide opportunities for in-depth study of subjects. With the help of network technologies, students can study regardless of their geographical location.

It is fact that with the help of network technologies, students have the opportunity to participate in team projects. The use of network technologies in education is reaching a new level. Within the framework of the Digital Uzbekistan 2030 strategy, large-scale work is being carried

out to introduce information technologies in schools and higher education institutions. For example, the Million Uzbek Coders project is aimed at teaching young people programming and information technology.

In addition, educational portals such as Ziyonet in Uzbekistan provide useful resources for students and teachers. Regarding to these platforms, students have the opportunity to gain new knowledge and consolidate existing knowledge.

Results and discussion. The ongoing work on digitalization of education in Uzbekistan can yield fruitful results in the future. The introduction of modern technologies in schools and universities will improve the level of knowledge of schoolchildren and students, as well as create an opportunity to prepare them for future professions.

The introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process has led to the creation of training using computer networks in addition to traditional teaching methods. An analysis of domestic and foreign sources (D. Cornelius, K. Danoff, D. McGregor, E.D. Patarakin, V.A. Polyakova, B. Smith, etc.) [2; 3; 4; 5] shows that the concept of the peer-to-peer model is considered a promising direction in higher professional education. In network education, this model is implemented through information and communication technologies: students interact in the educational community mode, making an equal contribution to solving common problems.

The efficiency of the learning process in the education system can be improved by using various approaches. Innovative approaches are a key condition for modernizing the education system and achieving educational efficiency.

Taking into account the relevance of the tasks set, the work considers the study and analysis of the use of local area networks in teaching computer science and information technology, the development of methods for their effective use and relevant methodological recommendations.

The purpose of the research work: To analyze the possibilities of using a local area network in the formation of students' knowledge in computer science and information technology, to identify the effective aspects of its use, and to study the state of its use in the educational process.

Research objectives: identifying the possibilities of using local area networks in teaching computer science and information technology.

Definitely, the introduction of computer training in educational institutions brings many advantages. Network training involves two approaches: individual and personal. Personal training is the student's attitude to his own education, that is, his awareness of the need to study a particular subject and receive information that will bring him the greatest benefit. Individual training is a model of organizing the educational process, in which the teacher interacts with only one student, taking into account his personal characteristics, creating psychological and pedagogical conditions for his development. This model assumes the presence of a mentor or teacher who builds a learning path for the student [6]

One of the modern programs that provides ample opportunities for learning in a school computer lab using the network and control from the teacher's computer is the Net Support School program.

It has the following capabilities:

- starting and shutting down student computers;
- providing students with the opportunity to work in small groups on their computers online;
- sending files and assignments to any student's computer;

-displaying information from any student's computer to the teacher's monitor and receiving the results of completing assignments;

-providing students' computers with the ability to access Internet sites, and, if necessary, monitoring and stopping their work;

Certainly, there are a number of other similar capabilities. The teacher performs these tasks by installing the Net Support School program on his computer and using its commands [7].

Net Support School will find all student computers with the same group name specified during installation, provided that the same range of IP addresses is used. Net Support School software displays them on the teacher's computer. Net Support School's screen mirroring feature allows the teacher's computer screen to be mirrored (displayed) on selected or all student monitors. The teacher uses this to explain the necessary parts of the subject material by showing them on the student's computer screen. If necessary, the teacher can divide the class into small groups and assign tasks to the students using the LAN. For example, if a group is divided into 5 subgroups, a student is designated as a leader of each subgroup and is given authority, and 5 leaders of each subgroup can be directed or supervised at a time.

Using the presentation feature, the teacher can lead discussions on the handouts.

-To assign a group leader, select the appropriate group tab.

-Right-click on a specific student's icon and select "Leader".

The teacher supervises the students' work via the LAN. This will allow students to work independently and think freely on the computer.

Net Support School's LAN software offers a screen recording feature. If a teacher has created a video lesson, this feature can be used to broadcast it without distribution.

Working with a local area network in the educational process involves mandatory individual work with educational materials, learning to work in small groups to solve complex problems, creating a presentation of the proposed solution, and holding a discussion during defense.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that formation of information knowledge and skills of students using network technologies is an important part of modern education. Due to the effective use of network technologies, you can prepare students for the digital world and improve their knowledge and skills. Their correct use will improve the quality of education and allow students to effectively use modern information technologies. Using a local area network is one of the most convenient and effective ways of learning, expanding the possibilities of independent learning for students. In the future, network technologies will be used more widely in education.

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